

PERCEPTION OF YOUTH AGE PREGNANCY WITH STRESS FACING LABOR IN TRIMESTER III PREGNANT WOMEN IN COMMUNITY HEALTH CENTER OF TANAH KALI KEDINDING SURABAYA

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ABSTRACT

Background: Pregnancy at adolescence is at high risk because it can cause fetal death. The reproductive system in adolescents is not ready for fetal growth and development. The first experience of labor is one of the causes of stress due to a lack of knowledge about the signs of labor and the severity of labor. Incomplete information, and not necessarily true, will lead to the perception that labor is a negative, frightening, and dangerous thing. Feeling anxious about something they will experience during labor so that it can cause stress which will affect the labor process.

Objectives: The purpose of this study was to analyze the relationship between perceptions of pregnancy and stress in facing labor.

Methods: This type of research uses the method *correlation analytic* conducted in April 2018, the population and samples of third trimester teenage pregnant women, the dependent variable perceptual and independent stress, this study used a total sampling technique, the measuring instrument used the questionnaire and used the test *chi square*.

Results: The results of the statistical test show that $p < 0.00$ ($\alpha < 0.05$) indicates that H_0 is rejected so that there is a strong relationship between the perception of pregnancy and stress facing labor.

Conclusion: Mothers who have positive perceptions or perspectives about pregnancy give rise to positive perceptions so that they do not experience stress or only experience mild stress that will help smooth the delivery process.

Key words: Perception Pregnant, Teen, Stress, Delivery.

INTRODUCTION

Adolescents are a transition person who gradually exhibits the characteristics of a woman or a man until it reaches biological maturity, his soul develops from childhood to adulthood, and his socio-economic conditions change from dependence on parents to be gradually free. The main problem faced by teenagers today is the faster the reproductive age comes. If a hundred

years ago a woman got her first menstruation (*menarche*) at the age of 17 years, then at this time the average age of a woman getting her first period is 12 years old. Marriage and pregnancy in adolescence contain a number of bad risks in the long term (Nurhajati, 2012). The reproductive age range that is still long, women who marry and become pregnant at the age of adolescents will have the opportunity to have large numbers of

children at the end of their reproductive age. Facing labor is one of the factors that can cause stress, considering that it is not only *somatic* but *psychosomatic*. Primigravida pregnant women usually get information about labor coming from friends and family. The information obtained usually tends to be limited to individual experiences and is only limited to pain and pain experienced during labor. Incomplete information, and not necessarily true, will lead to the perception that labor is a negative, frightening, and dangerous thing. Feeling afraid of something they will experience during labor so that it can cause stress which will affect the labor process.

The causes of stress include; stressors from outside the organization (*extra organizational stressors*), stressors from within the organization (*organizational stressors*), stressors from groups within the organization (*group stressors*), stressors from within the individual (individual stressors) (Anatan & Ellitan.2009). Based on the initial survey in October 2017 at the Community Health Center of Tanah Kali Kedinding, in 1 week there were 8 pregnant women who were partnered with young age 6 people expressed stress facing their labor. They said that this happened because of the first experience of labor. So that they are afraid of pain and the dangers that arise during childbirth.

Stress is one of the causes of prolonged labor at risk of fetal death, labor $\pm$ 5% of causes of maternal mortality in Indonesia. The Indonesian Demographic and Health (SDKI) survey results in 2012 showed that the Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) was 32/1000 live births, Maternal Mortality Rate (MMR) of 359 / 100,000.

According to Farida (2014) in adolescents the reproductive organs are functioning which are characterized by the

occurrence of menstruation, enlarged breasts, growth of hair in the armpits and genitals but are not ready for fetal growth. This condition can endanger the fetus and the risk of maternal and fetal death will occur. In addition, changes in the psychology of adolescents also change marked by sensitive, temporal, excessive reactive and negative emotions that can perceive this pregnancy in accordance with growth and development. Pregnancy in young adolescents can also cause stress, the first experience of labor is one of the causes of stress due to a lack of knowledge about the signs of labor and the severity of labor so that the stress experienced by *primigravid* continues and increases during the pregnancy will have implications for the mother's soul and the baby in the womb makes it difficult for labor. Stress can be caused by many factors. Elements that greatly affect the labor process and cause stress in pregnant women at a young age are the irregular contractions of the uterus and pain before labor.

Nurses as active health workers provide related information about the physiology of pregnancy and signs of labor carried out in the form of counseling programs where pregnant women in the third trimester and how to control stress.

The purpose of this study was to analyze the relationship of perceptions of pregnancy with stress facing labor.

METHODS

Study Design

This type of research is a correlation analytic study with an approach Cross Sectional.

Setting

This study was conducted at the Community Health Center of Tanah Kali

Kedinding in the District of Kenjeran Surabaya, conducted in April 2018.

Research Subject

The population is pregnant women in the third trimester primigravida age at the Community Health Center of Tanah Kali Kedinding, Kenjeran District with 36 respondents. Sampling was conducted at the Community Health Center of Tanah Kali Kedinding, Kenjeran District Surabaya using the total sampling technique with a sample of 36 respondents.

Instruments

Data on pregnancy perception and labor stress data were collected by questionnaire sheet.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was tested using SPSS 20.0 with statistical tests *Chi Square*.

Ethical Consideration

This research has gone through an ethical test from the Adi Husada Nursing Academy, Surabaya and obtained permission from the Health Resources of Surabaya Health Department.

RESULTS

Based on the results of the collection of data from 36 respondents obtained the general data of respondents that included age, Educational Level, Occupational, Pregnancy Perceptions, and Stress Level.

Characteristics of Respondents by Age

Table 1. Distribution of Frequency of Respondents by Age in the Community Health Center of Tanah Kali Kedinding in April 2018 (n = 36).

Age	Frequency	(%)
13-15 th	8	22.2
16-19 th	28	77.8
Total	36	100

Based on table 1 found that most of the respondents' age in the Community Health Center of Tanah Kali Kedinding, Surabaya aged 16-19 years, as many as 28 respondents (77.8%).

Characteristics of Respondents by Gender

Table 2. Distribution of Frequency of Respondents by Educational Level in the Community Health Center of Tanah Kali Kedinding in April 2018 (n = 36).

Educational Level	Frequency	(%)
Elementary School	14	39
Junior High School	12	33.3
Senior High School	10	27.7
Total	36	100

Based on table 2 found that most of the respondents' educational level at the Community Health Center of Tanah Kali Kedinding which has elementary school, as many as 39 respondents (39%).

Characteristics of Respondents by Occupational

Table 3. Distribution of Frequency of Respondents by Occupational in the Community Health Center of Tanah Kali Kedinding in April 2018 (n = 36).

Occupational	Frequency	(%)
Working	10	27.8
Not working	26	72.2
Total	36	100

Based on table 3 found that most respondents work in the Community Health Center of Tanah Kali Kedinding which does not work, as many as 26 respondents (72.2%).

Characteristics of Respondents by Pregnancy Perceptions

Table 4. Distribution of Frequency of Respondents by Pregnancy Perceptions in the Community Health Center of Tanah Kali Kedinding in April 2018 (n = 36).

Pregnancy Perception	Frequency	(%)
Positive	30	83.3
Negative	6	16.7
Total	36	100

According table 4, it shows that the perception of mothers in Community Health Center of Tanah Kali Kedinding had positive perception of pregnancy by 30 people (83.3%).

Characteristics of Respondents by Stress Level

Table 5. Distribution of Frequency of Respondents by Stress Level in the Community Health Center of Tanah Kali Kedinding in April 2018 (n = 36).

Stress Level	Frequency	(%)
Normal	4	11.1
Mild	25	69.5
Moderate	7	19.4
Amount	36	100

Table 5 displays that stress levels mothers face normal labor 11.1%, mild 69.5% and moderate 19.4%.

Examination of Correlation of Pregnancy Perceptions and Stress Levels in Facing Labor in Pregnancy Trimester III at Youth Age

Table 6. Correlation of Pregnancy Perceptions and Stress Levels in Facing Labor in Pregnancy Trimester III at Youth Age in the Community Health Center of Tanah Kali Kedinding in April 2018 (n = 36).

Stres	Persepsi Positif		Negatif		Frekuensi	
	Frekuensi	%	Frekuensi	%	si	%
Normal	4	11,1	0	0	4	11,1
Ringan	20	55,5	5	14	25	69,5
Sedang	6	16,6	1	2,8	7	19,4
Berat	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sangat berat	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jumlah	30	83,2	6	16,8	36	100

Uji Chi Square p=0,00 α<0,05

Based on Table 6 shows that 4 respondents (11.1%) have positive and not stressed perceptions, while those who

experience stress mild there were 25 respondents (69.5%). The results of test *chi square* showed that $p = 0.00$ showed that there was a relationship between the perception of pregnancy and stress in facing labor.

DISCUSSION

Pregnancy perceptions

Based on the results of the study in table 6, it shows that most of the 30 respondents with a percentage of 83.3% who were observed showed positive perceptions. Perception is a process that involves the entry of messages or information into the human brain, through human perceptions while in the broadest sense is the view or vision, which is how one views or interprets something Slameto (2010). The factors that influence perception are functional resulting from the needs, excitement (mood), service, and past experience of an individual; Structural means factors that arise or result from the form of stimuli and neutral effects arising from the individual nervous system; Situational related to non-verbal language. Proxemic instructions, kinesics instructions, facial instructions, and paralinguistic instructions; Personal consists of experience, motivation, and personality. Most of the respondents have elementary school education, elementary school education should only be able to receive information without analyzing and most do not work but the respondents who do not work will spend more time at home.

Family is one of the factors that influence a person's perspective / perception, for example by providing information on experiences previously obtained, environmental factors can also influence perceptions such as what is usually held counseling from a local health center or

Integrated Service Post. In addition, information is also very easy to obtain with social media, print media so that even though most of the respondents do not work and the last is elementary school education, it is possible to get broad insights. The family and environment that take part play a role in providing information capable of influencing perceptions of positive pregnancy, for example, the mother always keeps her womb before delivery with good nutrition and positive activities such as recitation, counseling about pregnancy in the environment so that the perception of pregnancy remains positive until before delivery.

Labor stress

In table 6 shows that most of the 25 (69.5%) large-scale respondents experienced mild stress in facing labor. While 4 (11.1%) respondents did not experience stress. Stress itself is a condition that affects a person's physical or psychological state because of pressure from inside or outside someone who can interfere (Robbins, 2001). Stress that is too large can threaten a person's ability to deal with his environment. Primigravida pregnant women usually get information about labor coming from friends and family. The information obtained usually tends to be limited to individual experiences and is only limited to pain and pain experienced during labor. Incomplete information, and not necessarily true, will lead to the perception that labor is a negative, frightening, and dangerous thing. Feeling anxious about something they will experience during labor so that it can cause stress which will affect the labor process.

Most of the respondents had elementary school education and did not work, so they spent more time at home to rest more and

have time to do routine checks at the nearest Integrated Service Post or Community Health Center of and usually obtained information from local health workers. Respondents mostly experienced mild stress in dealing with childbirth by saying that it was very easy to be patient in facing pregnancy problems / problems such as pain by means of deep breathing exercises so that the body becomes relaxed like information provided by health center health workers and respondents said that they very enthusiastic about anything, for example, always taking part in counseling activities held by local health workers. Most respondents aged 16-19 years at this age include adolescents. Teenagers at this time are no stranger to gadgets, because it is one of the electronic medias that can provide information so that respondents are able to overcome their anxiety by finding sources of information about childbirth.

Relationship between perceptions of pregnancy and stress in childbirth

Based on table 6 The relationship of perceptions of pregnancy to the age of adolescents with stress facing childbirth in third trimester pregnant women in the Community Health Center of in the land lies on the wall. The results of the respondents' research which showed most of the 6 respondents had negative perceptions and 30 had positive perceptions. Based on the chi square test about the relationship of perceptions of pregnancy to the age of adolescents with stress facing childbirth in third trimester pregnant women obtained a result of 0.00. This shows there is a significant correlation between the perception of pregnancy with stress facing labor. Viewed from the level of the relationship (correlation coefficient) between variables according to test *chi square* which

ranged 0.00 indicates that the results of this study have a degree of correlation between the perception of pregnancy with stress facing labor. Mothers who have a positive outlook on pregnancy will experience normal to mild stress as well as mothers who are anxious and stressed can cause them to be afraid pain and danger that arise during childbirth, making it difficult for labor. This shows that stress facing labor cannot be separated from these factors which greatly influence labor. Maternal psychology greatly determines the success of labor. Stressed mothers will generally have difficulty in labor. Negative perceptions, the unhappiness of the mother in the period before labor greatly influences stress levels which can complicate labor.

CONCLUSION

Mothers who have positive perceptions of pregnancy experienced in the face of childbirth have stress in most mild levels, but in primigravida mothers who are under stress due to first experience, test *chi square* shows $p = 0.00$ with $\alpha < 0.05$ there is a relationship between the perception of pregnancy with stress facing labor, this means that the higher the intensity of the perception of a positive pregnancy, the lower the level of stress facing labor in primigravida mothers and vice versa.

SUGGESTION

1. For research land
 - a. Maintain programs that have been made by the government for pregnant women in the implementation of periodic pregnancy inspection programs.
 - b. Adding information by conducting counseling about the signs of labor and the emergency in labor is equipped with supporting media such as: videos, mannequins, brochures or posters.

2. For respondents
 - a. Increase knowledge about calm signs of labor and the severity of labor carried out by health workers, as well as through the development of media and electronics.
 - b. Carry out advice given by health workers in controlling stress.
3. The next researcher
can be used as a reference for the next researcher by adding the number of variables with the method of the three treatment groups and with one treatment group as the controller. Suggestion title Effect of audio therapy with stress facing labor in pregnant women.

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